

Deliverable 7.5

Initial Clustering Plan

Version 1

WP 7
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***IGNITION** – Improving **Green** Innovation for the blue revolu**TION**: new tools and opportunities for a more sustainable animal farming is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement: 101084651)*

Executive Summary

Clustering enables projects with similar objectives or complementary aspects to collaborate, thereby creating synergies that magnify their collective impact. By sharing knowledge, resources, and expertise, these projects can achieve outcomes far greater than what individual efforts could otherwise accomplish. This initiative is expected to avoid duplication of efforts while making sure that resources are allocated more efficiently, maximizing the overall effectiveness and impact of the projects involved.

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1. Objectives of the cluster

- i. Create synergies between projects: enabling projects with similar objectives or complementary aspects to collaborate, thereby magnifying their collective impact.
- ii. Optimize utilization of resources: by creating a communication channel between the projects, it is expected that duplication of efforts can be avoided, and that efforts invested can have higher impact.
- iii. Knowledge sharing: facilitating the exchange of ideas, best practices, and innovations among various projects.
- iv. Improve collaboration and networking: the collaborative environments formed through clustering can encourage networking among project participants, stakeholders, and experts, which may open avenues for future collaborations and partnerships.
- v. Amplify impact: by collaborating in the different output medias, all the project involved can gain higher visibility, reaching a broader public. A common communication by the projects with policymakers and other stakeholders can also amplify the projects impact by reducing stakeholder fatigue.
- vi. Improve coherence: Clustering projects can help align with overarching policies and strategies set by the European Union. This coherence ensures that efforts across different projects are harmonized, reinforcing the EU's broader objectives and agendas.

2. Integrating projects in the cluster

The goal of this cluster is to create synergies between European projects with similar goals and parallel activities and with other institutions or initiatives with similar aims. The projects to include in the cluster will be selected based on the following criteria:

- Projects invited in the cluster should share the following goals:
 - Reduce the use of veterinary drugs and the impact of diseases in aquaculture
 - Improve aquatic animal welfare and minimize the environmental impact of the aquaculture industry
 - Develop tools to mitigate the effects of stress
 - Develop breeding strategies for fish and shellfish
 - Improve fish immunization protocols and approaches
 - Use bioactive extracts to improve aquatic farmed animal's immune status
 - Study new non-invasive biomarkers of health and welfare
 - Develop methods of disease prediction
- Special focus will be given to projects in the same call/topic as IGNITION
- Projects from more recent Farm2Fork calls will be screened to search for potential synergies

- Funding by other entities other than the European Commission will not be considered as exclusion criteria, but the projects should, nevertheless, be transnational and focused on North-eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean species.

Projects should be aligned not only in goals but also, to an extent, in terms of timeframe. As such, projects finishing within the first year of IGNITION were not considered.

2.1. Projects in the cluster

As of now, IGNITION and three other projects have been integrated as a cluster:

2.1.1. Cure4Aqua

Will develop new approaches to prevent aquatic fish diseases by introducing and validating novel technologies for early detection of diseases, while also supporting the advancement of alternative treatments to replace pharmaceuticals in disease control. Its specific goals are:

- Develop cost-effective vaccines to prevent diseases in farmed fish
- Implement selective breeding programmes to improve stress and disease management
- Develop innovative, bio-based and sustainable alternatives to antibiotics for controlling fish diseases at various life stages
- Develop new tools and technology to improve fish health and welfare
- Improve diagnostics of fish pathogens
- Place fish welfare as a priority of aquaculture production by developing high welfare standards that consider different life-stages, production systems, and knowledge of welfare needs

2.1.2. GRINNAQUA

GRINNAQUA is a twinning project that is looking into improving CIIMAR's research quality. To this end, activities within GRINNAQUA will include the organization of workshops, summer schools and other training events in the field of aquatic animal health. The project also includes a scientific work package, aiming to study the role of dietary methionine in fish immune defences and disease resistance. The specific goals of the project are:

- To review the latest research and innovation advances in the sector, and identify and address institutional gaps and deficiencies
- To raise the staff's research profile and excellence via networking, training, and mentoring
- To increase stakeholder interaction and mobilization towards research and innovation partnerships
- To orientate research to contribute to economic growth and the implementation of the Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork strategies

- To establish an enabling environment for the development and maintenance of long-term international collaborations
- To deliver a framework for strengthening research and innovation in aquaculture

2.1.3. LOCALITY

The main objective of LOCALITY is to develop circular and sustainable value chains, linking industrial players to stimulate co-creation and bring new and innovative algae-based products to regional and global markets while protecting and restoring Europe's aquatic ecosystems. The algae sector can produce biomasses in many ways and deliver innovative products and ecological solutions, which have the potential to support the sustainability and security of food and feed systems and economic circularity.

Micro and macroalgae are rich in bioactive compounds that can have a positive effect in improving aquatic animal health. In LOCALITY, algae-based feed for aquaculture is produced and its effects on the animal immune status and their ability to fend off disease is assessed.

3. Communication channel

News synergies and opportunities for collaboration are constantly explored by holding monthly meetings between the project managers of the projects in the cluster. The meeting will take place every first Tuesday of the month. The following agenda points are common to all meetings:

- Look for opportunities to combine outreach and stakeholder engagement
- Focus on reducing stakeholder fatigue by targeting stakeholders in a more coherent way, avoiding the focus on individual projects but instead focusing on the messages

4. KPIs

The success of the cluster will be assessed by the number of joint activities.

4.1. Report on KPIs

1. XXIII Seminário de aquacultura
Showcasing and networking activity with aquaculture practitioners, organized by IGNITION and GRINNAQUA
26th May 2023, Setúbal, Portugal
2. Animal health and welfare in aquaculture: novel approaches for disease management.

Workshop, organized by Cure4Aqua & IGNITION.

11th September 2023, at the 21st International Conference on Diseases of Fish and Shellfish, Aberdeen, UK.

3. Industry stand at the 21st International Conference on Diseases of Fish and Shellfish.
Organized by IGNITION & GRINNAQUA
11-14 September 2023, Aberdeen, UK.
4. Animal health and welfare in aquaculture
Workshop, organized by IGNITION & Cure4AQUA
18th September 2023, at the Aquaculture Europe conference 2023, Vienna, Austria.
5. Industry stand at the Aquaculture Europe conference 2023
Collaborative stand with the Blue BioEconomy CoLab, by IGNITION and GRINNAQUA.
6. Data sharing between LOCALITY and IGNITION to feed the machine learning algorithms allowing for a more robust and quicker development of non-invasive tools to determine animal welfare and predict the onset of diseases.

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¹ Dissemination level (DELETE ACCORDINGLY): **PU**: Public, **CO**: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), set out in Model Grant Agreement, **CL**: Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

² Nature of deliverable (DELETE ACCORDINGLY): **R**: Report, **DEM**: Demonstration, pilot, prototype, plan design, **DEC**: Website, patent filing, market studies, press & media, videos, **Other**: Software, technical diagram, etc., **Ethics**: Ethics deliverable

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